

WORLD CONTEXTS OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP, AS SUPPORT FOR SPECIFIC ECONOMIC CONTEXTS OF MOUNTAIN INVESTMENTS

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Abstract

Exploring the nuances of entrepreneurship necessitates a deep dive into the prevailing economic landscape, with a specific focus on mountainous regions. The dynamics of self-employment manifest with greater prominence in less economically developed countries and regions, where the informal sector and illegitimate practices exert a dominant influence on labor markets and production organization. These areas typically grapple with challenges such as ineffective monitoring, reporting, and tracing mechanisms, which, in turn, may contribute to a dearth of new companies showcasing genuine development potential. Particularly in countries characterized by vast mountainous terrains and elevated poverty levels, there arises an imperative need for global investments.

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In the context of low investment areas, such as mountain regions, a multitude of innovative concepts may emerge and penetrate the market through successful informal enterprises. These ventures might even burgeon into integral components of value chains, albeit without legal registration. Despite their revenue-generating capacities, unregistered businesses remain excluded from official reporting channels, notably in national accounts, thus fostering an underground economy. This phenomenon is especially prevalent in mountainous areas, where the challenging operational conditions, surpassing those in other topographical settings, compel mountain entrepreneurs to engage in the clandestine economic activities of a country. In nations with inadequately safeguarded economies, mountainous regions often witness the proliferation of the underground economy, a consequence of limited protections and insufficient incentives for entrepreneurs. This scenario gives rise to a spectrum of economic activities ranging from black and gray to informal and illegal, as elucidated by Desai (2017).

A comprehensive global investigation, encompassing countries eager to participate, undertook an adult population survey (PHC) as part of the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) initiative. The Adult Population Survey (APS), administered to a minimum of 2000 adults in each

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participating country, serves as an intricate questionnaire designed to gather exhaustive insights into entrepreneurship, encompassing the attitudes and aspirations of respondents. The outcomes of this expansive study unveil compelling statistics shedding light on the intricacies of entrepreneurship and innovation within a given country. The interplay between economic contexts, entrepreneurship, and mountain investments becomes increasingly evident as we delve into the multifaceted layers of this research endeavor.

(figure 1)

Figure 1. Percentage of those involved in TEA - business services sector: information and communications, financial and real estate intermediation, professional or administrative services, as defined by ISIC 4.0

Source: <https://www.gemconsortium.org/data>

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The statistics are presented as a percentage (%), in relation to the maximum potential of 100%. At European level, Western and Nordic countries are showing good results in the sustainability of entrepreneurship, not necessarily through the establishment of new businesses, but rather through the development of existing ones. The situation is different in the countries of South-Eastern Europe. Thus, in Romania, the perceived opportunities are 33.30 percent (the proportion in which respondents consider that there are certain entrepreneurial opportunities); Perceived capabilities 46.30 (represents the percentage of existence of entrepreneurial capacity); Fear of failure 40.50; Entrepreneurial intentions 29.00; Entrepreneurial activities in the early stages - total (TEA) 10.80; Commercial property 7.50; Entrepreneurial activity of employees 4.60; Motivation index 1.20; TEA - Women / Men 0.50; TEA - opportunities developed by Women / Men 1.10; High job creation expectations 39.80; Innovation 30.00; Business Sector related to services 17.60; Successful entrepreneurs 75.10; Entrepreneurship - career option 72.40.

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The indicators replicated in the other European countries that report entrepreneurial statistics are:

- Austria: 31.20; 53.30; 36.80; 4.10; 6.20; 7.80; 7.00; 0.80; 0.50; 36.60; 79.80; 44.50.

- Croatia: 47.20; 75.00; 52.10; 24.30; 12.70; 4.20; 7.70; 0.60; 21.50; 33.70; 53.50; 59.30.

- Cyprus: 21.10; 58.10; 49.10; 20.50; 8.50; 7.30; 6.40; 0.60; 32.70; 41.00; 70.70; 76.70.

- Germany: 36.00; 47.60; 31.00; 10.70; 4.80; 6.20; 5.90; 0.90; 24.90; 29.80; 81.80; 54.90.

- Greece: 27.90; 53.20; 53.10; 11.30; 8.60; 14.60; 2.50; 0.60; 12.70; 17.50; 70.30; 69.50.

- Italy: 62.20; 60.80; 28.40; 4.50; 1.90; 2.20; 1.10; 0.30; 2.30; 23.40.

- Latvia: 37.10; 55.30; 41.60; 17.20; 15.60; 11.10; 3.50; 0.60; 29.80; 21.20; 61.80; 56.70.

- Luxembourg: 41.90; 45.70; 42.30; 11.10; 8.00; 3.60; 4.50; 0.50; 34.00; 43.60.

- Netherlands: 48.80; 43.60; 38.20; 13.10; 11.50; 7.00; 1.70; 0.70; 13.50; 41.20.

- Norway: 57.00; 41.60; 27.40; 5.60; 7.60; 4.10; 4.90; 0.50; 28.40; 41.80.

- Poland: 51.60; 60.00; 41.20; 4.70; 3.10; 12.20; 1.40; 0.60; 21.60; 25.40;
60.10; 59.90.

- Russia: 33.40; 34.50; 46.50; 8.30; 8.50; 4.70; 0.40; 0.70; 43.30; 17.10;
72.50; 75.30.

- Slovakia: 40.90; 56.40; 48.70; 13.80; 13.80; 6.50; 3.40; 0.50; 28.80; 33.80;
62.10; 49.30.

- Slovenia: 42.00; 59.40; 43.80; 11.90; 6.00; 7.00; 6.50; 0.70; 24.70; 22.70;
85.10; 68.70.

- Spain: 16.50; 51.90; 53.60; 6.80; 5.20; 6.70; 1.30; 0.90; 8.70; 30.80; 61.10;
56.70.

- Sweden: 62.50; 52.10; 42.80; 8.30; 7.30; 6.00; 6.10; 0.50; 15.70; 34.40.

- Switzerland: 26.70; 44.50; 33.40; 7.30; 9.20; 6.70; 7.30; 0.90; 9.50; 33.60;
71.90; 49.30.

- Great Britain: 27.30; 54.50; 48.30; 8.20; 7.80; 6.50; 6.50; 0.70; 16.40;
26.40; 77.10; 69.60.

The indicators of entrepreneurial behavior and attitudes measured by the
Adult Population Survey (PHC) take into account:

- Perceived opportunity rate: Percentage of the population 18-64 (people
involved in any stage of entrepreneurial activity, exclusively) who see good
opportunities to start a company in the area where they live.

- Perceived capacity rate: Percentage of the population 18-64 (people involved in any stage of entrepreneurial activity, exclusively) who consider that they have the skills and knowledge needed to start a business.
- Fear of failure: Percentage of the population 18-64 (people involved in any stage of entrepreneurial activity, exclusively) who are afraid of failure in setting up a business.
- Rate of entrepreneurial intentions: Percentage of the population 18-64 (people involved in any stage of entrepreneurial activity, exclusively) with latent entrepreneurs and who intend to start a business within three years.
- Total rate of entrepreneurial activity in the early stages (TEA): Percentage of the population 18-64 who present either a developing entrepreneur or owner-manager of a new business.
- Current rate of business owners: Percentage of the population 18-64 who is currently the owner-manager of an established business, ie owns and manages functional businesses - pays salaries or makes any other payments for more than 42 months.
- Employee entrepreneurship rate: The rate of employee involvement in entrepreneurial activities, such as the development or launch of new goods or services, or the establishment of a new business unit, a new unit or a subsidiary.

- Motivational index: the percentage of those involved in ASD who are motivated by opportunities.

- TEA ratio between women and men: the percentage of the population aged 18-64 who is either an incipient entrepreneur or an owner-manager of a “new business”, divided by the equivalent percentage for their male counterparts.

- TEA opportunity ratio for women / men: The percentage of women involved in TEA and i) who say they can't find another job option, respectively (ii) who indicate that the main determinant of being involved in this opportunity is independence or growth their income, rather than maintaining income, divided by the percentage equivalent to their male counterparts.

- Expectation rate for job creation: Percentage of those involved in ASD who expect to create 6 or more jobs in 5 years.

- Innovation rate: The percentage of those involved in TEA that indicates that their product or service is new to at least some customers and that few companies offer the same product.

- Business services sector rate: Percentage of those involved in TEA in the “Business services” sector - information and communication, financial and real estate intermediation, professional or administrative services, as defined by ISIC 4.0.

- Success rate of entrepreneurs: Percentage of the population 18-64 who agree with the statement that in their country, successful entrepreneurs are in large numbers and have increased benefits.

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- Entrepreneurship as a high career choice rate: The percentage of 18-64 people who agree with the statement that in their country most people consider starting a business as a timely career choice.

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(<https://www.gemconsortium.org/data>)

According to statistics and qualitative studies conducted in the mountainous areas of Europe, independent activities are encountered in the countries of the South-East. The establishment of new companies and entrepreneurship at an early stage are ambivalent phenomena - sustainable in Western and Nordic countries, with a low degree of sustainability in the South-East. Necessity entrepreneurship is very common in all mountain areas, the vast majority of mountain businesses being set up as a result of a clear need, otherwise the failure of entrepreneurs is guaranteed. Opportunity entrepreneurship is rare in the mountainous areas of Europe, and it is used only in the case of a high opportunity such as the organization of championships in those areas, large-scale events, etc.

The paper represents a part of the Covaci, B. (2021), PhD (c) research report 1, Oradea University

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